

JUST WE ARE NOT VILLAGES: IDENTITY AND INVISIBILITY
AMONG PEOPLE ORIGINATING FROM PIRAQUÊ-AÇU, ARACRUZ-
ES³²

 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.8025686

*Márcio Antônio Farias de Freitas*³³

PhD in Anthropology. Master and Graduate in Social Sciences.

m.ffreitas@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

The municipality of Aracruz, located on the north coast of the State of Espírito Santo, is marked by the presence of Guarani and Tupiniquim indigenous peoples, as well as riverside dwellers and fishermen, who live on the banks of the Piraquê-açu River, whose mouth meets the Atlantic Ocean. , which, alongside the Atlantic Forest and the mangrove swamp, form a rich biodiversity of natural ecosystems, fundamental in the material and symbolic production and reproduction of human collectives. But this scenario was dramatically impacted in November 2015, due to the collapse of the Fundão dam, owned by Samarco Mineração S/A ³⁴, which occurred in Mariana, State of Minas Gerais, which spilled about 62 million cubic meters of ore tailings. iron and silica, among other elements. In my fieldwork for my doctorate, carried out in 2017 in Aracruz-ES, I came across an uncomfortable situation, since on the north bank of the Piraquê-açu river those affected were recognized as such, while those on the south bank remain to this day without this recognition. In this article, I intend to analyze this asymmetry in the treatment of those affected by Piraquê-açu, which permeates the recognition - or not - by the State of these collectives as indigenous.

Keywords: indigenous peoples - ethnic identity - self recognition - environmental crime - invisibility

Introduction

I carried out my field research for my doctorate in Anthropology in the community of Lajinha, located on the south bank of the Piraquê-açu river, in Aracruz, Espírito Santo, where,

³²Paper presented at the 1st International Scientific Congress of the International Network of Researchers on Native Peoples and Traditional Communities (RedeCT).

³³Researcher at the Center for Research in Anthropology (CRIA/Portugal), *Red Antropología Ambiental* (Spain) and Laboratory of Studies, Research and Experiments in Natures-Cultures (UFES/Brazil); in addition to being a member of the Portuguese Association of Anthropology (APA) and the Brazilian Association of Anthropology (ABA).

³⁴Currently controlled through a *joint venture* between Vale S/A and the Anglo-Australian BHP Billiton Ltd.

in a landscape of environmental degradation, caused by the biggest Brazilian environmental crime, which occurred in 2015, with the rupture of the Fundão dam, in Mariana-MG, managed by the mining companies Samarco, Vale and BHP Billiton, I sought to understand, through ethnography, how the collective it understood this phenomenon, organized itself and reacted, from its ontological perspectives, in a context marked by its invisibility and asymmetrical power relations.

In the on the banks of this Piraquê-açu river, many stories , traditional knowledge and indigenous customs are concentrated , since its population has always lived according to this ecosystem, where they have developed their material and symbolic production and reproduction for centuries.

These collectives underwent transformations in the configuration of their territories, whether in relation to changes in land ownership and land use and occupation, from the end of the 1940s onwards, due to the formation of large land properties - first dedicated to coal by Companhia Ferro and Aço de Vitória S/A (COFAVI) and later to the monoculture of eucalyptus by Aracruz Celulose S/A in the 60's -, either through the creation of the Piraquê-Açu and Piraquê-Mirim Mangrove Ecological Reserve in the 80's, which transformed free areas and extensions of properties in territories of a CU, starting to impose limits, borders, norms and restrictions, and which was accompanied by the urban occupation of this coastal region.

In this context of changes caused by these two logics - the neo-extractivist and the conservationist - is Lajinha , literally sandwiched between the eucalyptus of Suzano Celulose S/A and the Piraquê-açu and Piraquê-mirim Municipal Sustainable Development Reserve, administered by the Municipality of Aracruz. Lajinha is a collective united by kinship ties, an organizer of the social space (WOORTMANN, 1995), all members of the only family in the region that did not agree to sell the land to Aracruz Celulose S/A in the 1970s , arguing that they wanted their children to be raised there.

With a population of around 50 people, Lajinha has been abandoned by the municipal public authorities, lacking piped water, being supplied weekly by water trucks, and also not having any public equipment, forcing its residents to go to Santa Rosa or at the Aracruz Headquarters the services of education, health and commerce.

On the north bank of the Piraquê-açu River, there are two Indigenous Lands ³⁵recognized by FUNAI, the Tupiniquim Indigenous Land and the Caieiras Velha II Indigenous

³⁵ As defined by FUNAI, Indigenous Land (TI) is a portion of the national territory, owned by the Union, inhabited by one or more indigenous peoples, used by them for their productive activities, essential for the preservation of the environmental resources necessary for their well-being and necessary for their physical and cultural

Land. TI Tupiniquim has an approximate area of 14,282 hectares, located between the ES-257 highway and the Piraquê -açu river, and has a population of approximately 3,200 people, distributed in nine villages (Caieiras Velha, Irajá, Boa Esperança, Três Palmeiras, Amarelos, Areal, Olho D'Água , Nova Esperança and Pau Brasil), which, with the exception of the villages Boa Esperança, Três Palmeiras, Olho d´Água and Nova Esperança, formed by Guarani Mbyá Indians , the other villages are composed by Tupiniquim Indians. It was ratified in 2010 and unified the Caieiras Velha and Pau Brasil Indigenous Lands. TI Caieiras Velha II, adjacent to TI Tupiniquim and close to the mouth of the Piraquê -açu river , has an area of 57 ha and a population of 18 people, in its only village (Piraquê -açu), made up of Guarani Mbyá Indians .

In addition to these, on the coast of the municipality is the Comboios Indigenous Land, located between the Comboio rivers and the sea, with an area of approximately 3,800 hectares. Formed by Tupiniquim Indians and with a population of 706 people (FUNAI Indigenous Census 2017) , is distributed in two villages, Comboios and C ó rrego D`Ouro.

Table 01: Indigenous population of Aracruz

indigenous land		Village	indigenous people	Population	Source	legal framework
Caieiras Velha II		Piraquê -açu	Guarani Mbyá	18	FUNAI Census 2013	Federal Decree No. of April 19, 2004
Tupiniquim	Caieiras Velha	Caieiras Velha	Tupiniquim	1545	FUNAI Census 2016	Federal Decree No. 88,926 of October 27, 1983
		Irajá	Tupiniquim	531	FUNAI Census 2016	
		Good Hope	Guarani Mbyá	135	FUNAI Census 2013	
		Três Palmeiras	Guarani Mbyá	111	FUNAI Census 2016	
		yellow	Tupiniquim	27	FUNAI Census 2016	
		beach	Tupiniquim	189	FUNAI Census 2016	
		water eye	Guarani Mbyá	45	FUNAI Census 2013	
	New Hope	Guarani Mbyá	91	FUNAI Census 2017		
brazilwood	brazilwood	Tupiniquim	515	FUNAI Census 2013	Federal Decree No. 88.672 of September 5, 1983	

reproduction, according to their uses, customs and traditions. It is a specific type of possession, of an original and collective nature, which is not to be confused with the civilist concept of private property. The right of indigenous peoples to their traditionally occupied lands is configured as an original right and, consequently, the administrative procedure for demarcating indigenous lands is merely declaratory in nature. Therefore, indigenous land is not created by constitutive act, but recognized based on technical and legal requirements, under the terms of the 1988 Federal Constitution. and the rights over it are imprescriptible. Indigenous lands support the unique and irreplaceable way of life of the approximately 300 indigenous peoples that inhabit Brazil today. <http://www.funai.gov.br/index.php/nossas-acoas/demarcacao-de-terras-indigenas>.

trains	trains	Tupiniquim	543	FUNAI Census 2017	Federal Decree No. 88,601 of August 9, 1983
	Córrego D'Ouro	Tupiniquim	163	FUNAI Census 2017	

Source: FUNAI/CR from MG_ES /CTL.

NOTE: Area of TI Caieiras Velha according to Federal Decree s/nº of December 11, 1998, which increased it to 2,997 hectares. Area of the TI Pau Brasil according to Federal Decree s/nº of December 11, 1998, which increased it to 1,579 hectares. In 2010, with Federal Decree s/nº of November 5th, the Tupiniquim Indigenous Land was ratified, unifying the Caieiras Velha and Pau Brasil Indigenous Lands, with 14,282 hectares, and the expansion of the Comboios Indigenous Land , from 2,759 to 3,800 hectares.

-

-

Here everyone is an Indian, except those who are not.

By asking the Lajinha collective about which identity category best defined the person interviewed, giving the options of fisherman, crab collector, indigenous, riverside, farmer, quilombola or other, even though all are politically linked to the categories of fisherman, scavengers and/or riverside dwellers, the majority declared themselves indigenous. It is important to highlight the speech of a resident of Lajinha, known in the neighboring municipality of João Neiva, where he sells crab, as “Indio”, who, in addition to demonstrating the movement between communities, states that he is the grandson of a caboclo, a term commonly used in different languages. unfavorable contexts, such as repression and/or discrimination, to avoid indigenous identification:

my grandfather, my mother's father, was a caboclo from Pufferfish, but around here there are caboclos everywhere, right? And I didn't know my grandfather's father, but they said he was a crazy caboclo too. My father was a Tupiniquim from the village of Pau Brasil, as was my uncle's wife. Today everyone is mixed up, right?

In addition to this transit of indigenous people coming and going from Lajinha, there is historical evidence that the territory itself is indigenous. The Anthropological Report approved by FUNAI and published in the Official Press (DOU of 01/13/1997) provides evidence that the Lajinha region was part of the Irajá village, currently located only on the north bank of the Piraquê-açu river, when it states that “the The Irajá village has existed there since the 19th century, when the region was virgin forest and the Indians occupied both banks of the Piraquê-açu river” (MPF, 2005, p. 38), since Lajinha is located in the same direction as Irajá , on the south bank of the river. In the Final Report on the Re-study of the Identification of the Caieiras Velha, Pau Brasil and Comboios Indigenous Lands, prepared in 1994 by the FUNAI technical

group, when describing the past of the region, today constituted by the village of Irajá, there is the following record:

some Tupiniquim indigenous families constituted the Irajá village since the 16th century. XIX. There the great-grandparents and grandparents of Veranício Vicente were born and lived, who knows the story of his grandfather João Vicente, and of his great-grandfather Manoel Vicente. At the beginning of the century, Maria Loureiro's grandparents settled in Irajá, who had previously lived and married in Comboios. They settled and lived in Irajá until their death, along with other families of remnants. The whole region was virgin forest, both in the sense of Caieiras Velha and Aracruz. Communication was through trails in the middle of the forest. The Indians occupied both banks of the Piraquê-açu River (FUNAI, 1994, p. 47).

Another evidence that comes to indicate the indigenous history of the territory of Lajinha are the archaeological sites found in its surroundings. According to the RDS Management Plan, and shown in figure 03, in 2007 the archaeologist Cristiane Machado recorded two archaeological sites in Lajinha, called Porto do Bastião and Sambaqui da Lajinha. In 2009, while drawing up the Management Plan, archaeologist Henrique Valadares discovered yet another site in Lajinha, Sambaqui da Lajinha II (IEMA, 2009). The Porto do Bastião site is a fixed grinder-polisher, with a set of marks resulting from the making of polished objects, associated with pre-ceramic groups on the coast (TENÓRIO, 2003) , supported by a fixed rocky block, located in mangrove vegetation in apicum terrain, going down the trail at the base of a hill. And the Sambaqui de Lajinha is located on the north bank of the Piraquê-mirim river, close to a rocky outcrop (IEMA, 2009).

Photos 01 and 02: Fixed sharpener-polisher in Lajinha

Author: Márcio Freitas

Sambaqui da Lajinha II is located on the same property, in Porto do Bastião, on top of a hill. In addition to these, another fixed stone sharpener-polishing tool was recorded in the

region by the same archaeologist, not exactly in Lajinha, but on the south bank of the Piraquêmirim river , called Peixe Verde, with three fixed sharpening-polishing bases in an outcrop rocky in mangrove (*Ibid*).

The same applies to agriculture and the production of flour - as in the case of the tipiti, an instrument made from guaimbé straw, for squeezing the manioc mass to make flour -, as well as in relation to the orientation of all its activities through the cycles of the moon and tide, the knowledge of the collective in relation to the construction of instruments and the techniques used in hunting and fishing. They are the same as the ones used by the indigenous people on the north bank of the Piraquê-açu and have been handed down for generations, from father to son, made with wood, vines and bamboo found in the forest and mangrove swamps ³⁶:

Cavadeira: wooden instrument with an iron tip to capture oysters from canapós (mangrove roots).

Hook: cambará stick (*Gochnatia polymorpha*), about two meters long, the end of which forms a hook that is introduced into the burrow to move the crab from the bottom of the burrow to the shore.

Batim: wooden spear with two iron points for capturing all kinds of fish and crustaceans, but mainly crab and aratu.

Slingshot: four-pronged spear to catch fish, mainly chira.

Harpoon: spear with one end to capture stingrays and large fish, such as caramuru.

Juquiá: trap with two openings made of bamboo or bamboo and tied with a vine to capture the crab.

Quitandu: Juquiá from an opening to capture shrimp and moray eel.

Samburá: basket made of guaimbé vine to store fish, crab, crab, etc. after being captured.

Wait net and trawl net: fishing artifacts made with nylon lines for catching fish, the first being installed in the middle of the river for removal the following day, and the trawl net used by throwing it into the river and dragging it back to the immediate capture of the fish.

³⁶ Tagibibuia (*Tabebuia casinooides*) - wood from the forest used to make the coat. Seriba (*Avicennia schaueriana*) - black mangrove wood used to make Congo drum and box. Cattail (*Thypha domingensis*) - marsh plant used for handicrafts, mainly baskets and bags. Cipó Guaimbe (*Philodendron bipinnatifidum*) - vine from the woods used for crafts, sieve and samburá.

Photo 06: Fishing net**Author:** Márcio Freitas

Another activity carried out in Lajinha in a traditional way, transmitted through generations and based on the collective's knowledge of bioecological cycles, is the manufacture of cassava and beiju flour, in the flour houses, here called quitungo. Cassava is planted on the land of family groups, at the beginning of the rainy season, usually in November and on the waxing moon, according to a resident, “on that moon it has better growth and does not spoil”, and it extends throughout the whole summer, with the harvest taking place a year and a half later, in winter, mainly in July. Here, both in the planting and harvesting of cassava, and consequently in the production of manioc flour and beiju - moments of collective production and sociability - various facets of the relationship between man and nature are manifested, such as the abundance and scarcity of rain, cassava, and flour, making the life of the collective easier or more difficult (SAHLINS, 2017).

After harvesting the roots, in the quitungo, the cassava is peeled, then ground in a mortar or grated on a grater. The grated cassava is accommodated in a wooden trough, dug like a canoe, and then pressed in the tipiti (*tipi* = to squeeze and *ti* = liquid, in Tupi), a long basket of vegetable fibers, or a wooden press to dry the mass. Then, the compacted mass is crumbled to avoid fermentation and facilitate sifting, which comes right after, which homogenizes the weight of the flour, ending with its toasting in the oven to remove the moisture, being constantly stirred through a squeegee.

Lajinha's four quitungos are originally made of wattle and daub. These wattle and daub houses are built by interlacing vertical timbers fixed to the ground with horizontal beams , usually made of bamboo, tied together by lianas, forming a perforated wall that is then filled with clay. In these quitungos are the equipment for the manufacture of flour and its derivatives, with only beiju in Lajinha.

Photo 07: Quitungo de Lajinha

Author: Márcio Freitas

These quitungos are used by their respective family members, where the mutirão regime prevails, with the production basically intended for collective consumption. In addition, as one resident reports, their activities adapt according to the natural cycles of the period, and here he mentions the winter, when there is greater diversification, with greater emphasis on the cassava harvest and the production of flour:

In the winter I work more in the fields, mainly with manioc, I make flour and sell it to people, sometimes I sell it, sometimes it's for my own consumption, and what I sell is a lot of money, today a quarter of flour costs thirty reais , a quarter is ten liters or six kilos, at the fair the flour is R\$ 3.50 a liter, and a liter is 900 grams, here in the countryside we buy it on Wednesdays, we make the flours in the delicacies we have here, I make them here.

In addition to its relationship with fish, crabs, crabs, oysters and other members of the rivers and mangroves around Piraquê, the collective has an intense relationship with its birds, cats and domestic dogs, which accompany them in all activities of the day, at home, in the mangroves and in the fields, in addition to being their guards who warn when strangers approach in the dark of night. And, although the presence of cattle, horses and pigs was not verified, all families have small enclosures with chickens, ducks and ducks on their properties, which keep them with eggs and their own meat, being an alternative source and guarantee of protein.

Due to the fact that they have had a close relationship with plants since they were children, they have great knowledge about the use of various species in the forest and agriculture, having small swiddens of cassava, beans, coffee and sugar cane, in addition to having mango trees. , breadfruit, guava, pitanga, banana, mastic and black pepper plants, but, according to a former resident: “the farm takes up a lot of our time, but the money comes from the mangroves, so we can't spend as much time on the rock”. And even if the lack of water is the main limiting factor for them to invest in agriculture, the majority still have vegetable gardens and small gardens on their land, but mainly medicinal plants, called medicine. She says that with the lack of water, the most difficult thing is to keep the vegetables, which need more water, “the most I can do with myself is a mint and a rosemary, which cannot be missing, right?”.

The relationship with the Atlantic Forest also brought residents a great deal of knowledge in relation to medicinal plants and roots, and it is common to plant herbs around the houses, as is the case of this resident, who has several, essential in her daily life. day, such as carambola, which is a fruit but is also indicated for blood pressure control, breadfruit leaf tea, which is indicated for kidney problems and banana leaf tea for hepatitis, in addition to mastic , which is healing, demonstrating great medicinal knowledge of plants:

it's very difficult for me to use pharmacy medicine, I don't need to use it, only herbal medicine. I learned all this from the older ones and I know that pharmacy medicine is harmful to people's health, this one is not harmful. What I really like is this bush tea, and there are people who have the medicine at home and use the medicine from the pharmacy.

Final considerations

In our eternal need to create the “other” (LOBÃO, 2010), in this case that “other” being the indigenous, Eduardo Viveiros de Castro calls our attention when he states that “anthropologists want, precisely, to guarantee this indigenous identity, only that do not guarantee; only the Indian ³⁷is guaranteed” (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2006, p. 44). Thus, in Lajinha, those who said they were indigenous feel indigenous, not dealing with an ontology of difference, where the indigenous identity would only be constituted belatedly by the determination of various elements at play, but by being a great-grandson, grandson, or son of an indigenous person. from some village, that is, he feels like an Indian, regardless of his relationship with another:

Indigenous people are not a matter of feather headdresses, annatto and bows and arrows, something apparent and evident in that stereotypical sense, but rather a matter of “state of mind”. A way of being and not a way of appearing. In fact, something more (or less) than a way of being: Indianness designated for us a certain *way of becoming*, something essentially invisible but no less effective for that reason: an infinitesimal incessant movement of differentiation, not a massive state of “difference”. ” anteriorized and stabilized, that is, an identity (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2006, p. 42).

Furthermore, who are we anthropologists to define who is or is not an Indian? Especially because we cannot play the role of a customs inspector pointing out who is an Indian or not, whether Lajinha is indigenous or not. It is up to us to create theoretical conditions to allow the interested collectives to articulate their Indianness, “only we are not villagers, but they are all our relatives too”, as a longtime resident of Lajinha said.

That is, the self-definition of the collective must be carried out by the collective itself, and by no one else, therefore, we can show that they are recognized by others as indigenous - except, at that moment, by the State -, who have the same traditional practices and knowledge as the indigenous collectives located on the north bank of the Piraquê-açu river, as well as all the historical evidence that points to the indigenous ancestry of the territory of Lajinha, since:

no matter how successful the de-indianization process carried out by catechization, missionarization, modernization, citizenship has been or is being, it is not possible to erase history and suppress all memory, because

³⁷In his text “In Brazil, everyone is an Indian, except those who are not”, Eduardo Viveiros de Castro defines an Indian as “any member of an indigenous community, recognized by it as such” and an indigenous community is “every community founded on relationships of kinship or neighborhood among its members, which maintain historical-cultural ties with pre-Columbian indigenous social organizations” (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2006, p. 41).

human collectives exist crucially and eminently at the moment of its reproduction, in the intergenerational passage of that relational mode that “is” the collective” (*Ibid.*, p. 45).

Evidences indicate the indigenous identity of the collective and its territory, and, in this, they have a material, symbolic, ancestral, spiritual, ethical and affective bond, although being an Indian is much more than having territory (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2006). And although they have the same relationship with the land, the river, the mangroves, the animals, the plants, the lunar and tidal cycles, and that they have the same collection, fishing, planting, harvesting and flour manufacturing practices, and, most importantly, most of the collective identifies itself as indigenous, it does not have the recognition of the State, much the result of a context of invisibility of indigenous groups, as discussed by João Pacheco de Oliveira (1998), since the State still reproduces a colonial vision of the “other”, hoping to find a naked Indian, painted with annatto and genipap, wearing a feather headdress and seed necklaces, with a bow and arrow or blowgun in his hands, hunting in the forest, establishing “external and arbitrary criteria to define what is (or what should be) a culture, or an indigenous culture in particular” (OLIVEIRA, 1999, p. 117).

Supporting itself, therefore, on external, phenotypic and stereotyped characteristics, which have long been rejected by ILO Convention No. 169, disregarding symbolic aspects and the organization of the collective inserted therein, fundamental in the constitution of its identity. And, according to Eduardo Viveiros de Castro, to be or not to be an Indian here would be much more a “state of mind”, a “becoming”, a way of being and not a way of appearing (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2006).

But would the Lajinha collective be forced to recognize itself as indigenous in order to receive emergency financial aid from the Renova Foundation³⁸, since in the Indigenous Lands, on the north bank of that river, all families were recognized and received this emergency, thus existing on the banks of the same river, citizens more citizens than others (MOTA, 2007)? Will he be entitled to have rights (ARENDRT, 1989) only if he is recognized as an indigenous person by the State (VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, 2017a)? Could it be that just being hit by “Samarco mud” would not be enough for that? And, as if that weren't enough, isn't the collective a

³⁸ The Renova Foundation is a private non-profit non-governmental organization, created in March 2016 by the Term of Transaction and Adjustment of Conduct (TTAC), and began operations on August 2 of the same year. It has the duty to repair the damage caused by the rupture of the Fundão dam, which occurred in November 2015 at the facilities of the mining company Samarco located in Bento Rodrigues, district of Mariana, Minas Gerais, conducting the repair and compensation of the damage caused by the disaster, through of the 42 TTAC programs (UNIÃO, 2016).

traditional community, whose National Policy for the Sustainable Development of Traditional Peoples and Communities guarantees it a series of rights?

And, although the collective's potential for political agency is low, restricting itself to denouncing the lack of interest in its situation on the part of the various institutional and non-institutional instances involved in the process, participating in several meetings, as well as waiting for an external solution to their problems, they have the possibility of accessing their rights enshrined in legal frameworks, such as Federal Decree No. 6,040/07, which establishes the PNPCT. That is, their rights guaranteed by law have not yet been recognized, because regardless of whether the collective is not recognized as an indigenous people, it was enough to be respected for being a traditional community, not least because one of the specific objectives of the PNPCT is precisely to ensure the full exercise of individual and collective, especially in situations of conflict or threat to their integrity; as well as “guarantee the rights of peoples and traditional communities directly or indirectly affected by projects, works and undertakings” (BRASIL, 2007b, Art. 3°).

However, several principles and objectives of the PNPCT are not being put into practice, with no recognition and consolidation of their rights; the collective being restricted from its full exercise of citizenship, living completely invisible, without regular and permanent access to food security, “without compromising access to other essential needs, based on food practices that promote health, that respect cultural diversity and that are environmentally, culturally, economically and socially sustainable”; there is no promotion of their quality of life, “guaranteeing the same possibilities for future generations and respecting their ways of life and traditions”; their right to socio-environmental, economic and cultural pluralities “that interact in different biomes and ecosystems” is not being respected; access to the natural resources they traditionally use for their physical, cultural and economic reproduction is not being guaranteed; many less are being recognized, protected and promoted their rights over their traditional knowledge, practices and uses (BRASIL, 2007b, Art. 1 and Art. 3).

That is why there is an urgent need for the collective to be recognized as affected by Samarco's tailings, which suffer from the same problems in the same way, as do all the collectives that live on the banks of the Piraquê, regardless of whether or not they are recognized as indigenous by the State. And, in addition to being worthy of receiving emergency financial aid from the Renova Foundation, one should not think only of this immediate perspective and focused only on this environmental crime, since, in addition to being essential to think about the impacts in a synergistic way, since they suffer for decades with the impacts caused by neo-

extractivism in Aracruz, it is also necessary to think about how they can once again have drinking water, the Atlantic Forest and abundant fauna.

References

ARENDRT, H. **Origins of totalitarianism**. Sao Paulo: Cia. of Letters, 1989.

BRAZIL. **Decree No. 6040** , of February 7, 2007. Establishes the National Policy for the Sustainable Development of Traditional Peoples and Communities. Brasilia, 2007.

NATIONAL INDIAN FOUNDATION. **Report on the restudy of the identification of the Caieiras Velha, Pau Brasil and Comboios indigenous lands**: Grupo Técnico, Ordinance N° 0783/94, of August 30, 1994 . Rio de Janeiro: FUNAI: Museu do Índio, 1994.

STATE INSTITUTE FOR THE ENVIRONMENT AND WATER RESOURCES.
Management Plan for the Piraquê-açu and Piraquê-mirim Mangrove Ecological Reserve . Vitória - ES, 2009.

LOBÃO, R. **Political cosmologies of neocolonialism**: how a public policy can become a policy of resentment. Niterói: EdUFF, 2010.

FEDERAL PROSECUTION OFFICE. **Recommendation No. 003**, of May 12, 2015. Recommends the publication of new acts of recognition of Indigenous Lands located in the state of Espírito Santo (Caieiras Velha, Pau Brasil and Comboios), totaling 18,070 hectares of surface. Public Prosecutor's Office in the State of Espírito Santo. Vitória, 2005.

MOTA, FR **When the city becomes the environment**: anthropological notes on environmental conflicts in Brazil. In: Proceedings of the First International Conference of Young Urban Researchers (FICYUrb). Lisbon, 2007.

OLIVEIRA, JP de. **Essays in Historical Anthropology**. Rio de Janeiro: Editora UFRJ, 1999.

_____. **An ethnology of the 'mixed indians'?** colonial situation, territorialization and cultural flows. In: The return trip: ethnicity, politics and cultural re-elaboration in the indigenous Northeast. Rio de Janeiro: Back cover, 1998.

SAHLINS, M. **The original affluent society**. In: _____. *Stone age economics* . New York and Abingdon: Routledge, 2017, p. 01-37.

TENÓRIO, MC **Stationary grinders-polishers** . Archeology Magazine, n° 16: 2003, p. 87-108.

UNITY; Government of the State of Minas Gerais; Government of the State of Espírito Santo; Samarco Mineração S/A; Vale S/A; BHP Billiton Brasil Ltda. **Term of Transaction and Adjustment of Conduct - TTAC** . Brasilia, 2 Mar. 2016.

VIVEIROS DE CASTRO, E. **In Brazil, everyone is an Indian, except those who are not.** Socio-environmental Institute . 2006.

_____. **What we are seeing on the planet today is a fight between peoples and not between classes. Or classes are re-defining themselves as peoples.** Environmental racism. May 19, 2017a. Available in: [https://racismoambiental.net.br/2017/05/19/o-que-est-a-mos-vendo-no-plane t a-hoje-e-um-combate-de-povos-e-nao-de-classes-or-classes-are-returning-to-define -as-peoples/](https://racismoambiental.net.br/2017/05/19/o-que-est-a-mos-vendo-no-plane-t-a-hoje-e-um-combate-de-povos-e-nao-de-classes-or-classes-are-returning-to-define-as-peoples/)

WOORTMANN, E. **Heirs, Relatives, and Compadres** : Southern Colonists and Northeast Besiegers. São Paulo - Brasilia: HUCITEC - Edunb, 1995.